

Measuring Uncertainty Perception in the Health Domain

1 Layperson summary

When people perceive more uncertainty about the risks they face, they may, somewhat counterintuitively, do less in terms of prevention effort. For instance, being unsure about the health risks they face, they may fail to adopt healthy behavior. In this project, we measure people's uncertainty perception about their health care expenditures and test how personalized information about health risks impacts their preventive health investments.

2 Background of the study and relationship to the literature

The prevention of suboptimal health behavior and the cultivation of positive care-seeking behaviors are crucial not only for individual wellbeing, but also for the control of healthcare costs at the policy level. It has been well-documented that individual health decisions—including preventative actions and engagement in risky behaviors—are influenced by personal perceptions of uncertainty and individual preferences (O'Donoghue and Somerville, 2018; Oster, Shoulson, and Dorsey, 2013; Anderson and Mellor, 2008). Specifically, perceiving more uncertainty about the risks faced (i.e. perceiving more “ambiguity”, as it is called since Ellsberg, 1961) can lead to underprevention as theoretically demonstrated by Baillon et al. (2022).

The empirical literature decomposes attitudes towards ambiguity into three components: (i) an (average) risk estimate, (ii) ambiguity aversion, i.e. disliking unclear risks, and (iii) a perception component measuring the imprecision of the risk estimate and generating insensitivity to that estimate.

While it has been demonstrated that these components of ambiguity attitudes significantly affect individual behaviors in various sectors, such as investment decisions in the financial domain (Dimmock et al., 2016), empirical application to health behavior remains limited. The main reason is that methods proposed to measure the three components are not suited for situations in which people can, themselves, influence the risks they face by their behavior. For instance, Baillon et al. (2018) proposed a method that extracts the three components from choices. It has been used in financial settings, for instance in the LISS panel, but it relies on the assumption that the risks are independent of people's behavior. In this project, we will propose a method to overcome this limitation.

3 Research questions

We plan to tackle three research questions:

1. Do people have accurate risk estimates about their future health expenditures?
2. Is perceived ambiguity associated with underprevention?
3. Does a personalized risk assessment intervention increase people's prevention effort via a reduction of the perceived ambiguity?

We will test the effects of a scalable personalized intervention, where we inform the respondents about the health risks of those with identical characteristics to theirs, on the respondents' health preventive effort and perception of uncertainty around health expenditures. Crucially, we will provide the respondents with true information about the health expenditures, based on the actual medical expenditures of people with the same average characteristics of those in our study.

Tackling these research questions will involve one main methodological challenge: adapting existing methods to health and to situations in which the uncertainty is influenced by people themselves.

4 Methodological approach

We aim to conduct a comprehensive study in early 2024, involving 2,500 respondents for 15 minutes. Access to demographic data, administrative records of health-care expenditures, and self-reported care-seeking behaviors of these respondents is necessary to form a comprehensive foundation for our analysis. In addition, access to the data from "Household decisions over the life-cycle" (Hans-Martin von Gaudecker; Christian Zimpelmann; Axel Wogroly) is needed to benchmark our measurement of risk and ambiguity attitudes with existing measurement in LISS.

The sample will be randomly split between one control group, and an intervention group. The intervention group will receive a personalized health risk assessment. This personalized assessment is based on what we are calling 'virtual twins'. These twins are not actual individuals but statistical representations of individuals who share similar demographic characteristics with our participants, and whose healthcare investment decisions are available in the CBS database. The purpose of these virtual twins is to provide an illustrative mirror image of potential health outcomes based on decisions made by similar individuals. It is a way to present a reflection of the participants' potential health risks. This approach enables participants to understand the

potential impact of their decisions on their health and healthcare costs, thereby shedding light on how uncertainty is managed and navigated. The risk assessment will be based on *past data*.

Following this intervention, we will measure respondents' attitudes towards ambiguity by adapting existing indexes from the financial and abstract domains to the health context. This will allow us to investigate how individuals' attitudes towards uncertainty can change when confronted with personalized health risk information. Moreover, we will measure future self-reported care seeking behavior and insurance choices.

We plan to adapt the method of Baillon et al. (2018) to healthcare expenditures—where the uncertainty can be directly influenced by decision-makers themselves. Instead of betting on the uncertainty they face themselves (as in the original method) and which they could influence, they will bet on the uncertainty faced by their 'virtual twin'. The approach to build the twins will be the same as the one we use for the personalized assessment of the intervention group. However, the people will bet on the *future* of their virtual twins (the following month).

First, we will assess the predictive power of the three components we measure (people's risk estimate, ambiguity aversion, and ambiguity perception) by investigating their ability to explain participants' care-seeking behaviors, insurance choices, and medical expenditures, using data from the control group. This validation process will underline the practical relevance of our measures in real-world health contexts, providing valuable insights for both researchers and policymakers.

Subsequently, we will compare ambiguity perception and risk estimates between the intervention group (those who received the personalized health risk assessment) and the control group (those who did not). This comparison will allow us to validate the effect of the personalized risk assessment on individual uncertainty perceptions.

Then we will study the impact of the intervention on care-seeking behaviors, insurance choices, and medical expenditures. This comparison will provide insights into the impact of personalized risk information on health-related decisions. We will also analyze the heterogeneity of the intervention's impact by considering factors such as education, socioeconomic status, and gender. This analysis will help us identify any patterns or disparities in how different demographic groups respond to personalized health risk information.

Our approach will not only enhance our understanding of health behavior, but also equip policy makers with valuable tools to encourage positive health decisions. We will validate these new

measures by correlating them with existing indices and by evaluating their predictive power in real-world scenarios. By doing so, we aim to create a robust platform for evidence-based policy making, ultimately promoting better health outcomes and more efficient use of healthcare resources.

File name	Volume (years)	Motivation for use
Health Expenditures (Zvwzorgkostentab)	2019-2020	We want to study the predictive power of our measures of ambiguity attitudes on the actual care seeking behavior, that we proxy using CBS data about medical expenditures at individual level.
Personal Characteristics (Gbapersoonktab)	1999-2021	Personal characteristics of the population to design “virtual twins” in order to incentivize the respondents’ answers.
Socio Economic Status (Secmbus)	1999-2021	Personal characteristics of the population to design “virtual twins” in order to incentivize the respondents’ answers.

5 Implications for research, practice and/or society

By testing the impact of a personalized health risk assessment intervention on preventive behavior, we will assess whether a simple and scalable intervention could help in reducing ambiguity around one’s health and increasing people’s effort in care seeking behavior.

Previous research has highlighted the importance of ambiguity attitudes in many settings such as financial decisions, but not much has been done empirically concerning health. For example, someone who perceives a health situation as more ambiguous may be willing to insure more but, somewhat counterintuitively, to exert less prevention effort. Understanding the link between ambiguity attitudes and health behavior is crucial while shaping the future of health care in the face of new threats. This is especially true in the Netherlands where 10% of the total GDP is devoted to health expenditures (CBS, 2020).

By understanding the underlying link between ambiguity attitudes and health decisions, we will open a potentially new channel to increase medical take up. Most importantly, by disentangling whether the heterogeneity in care seeking correlates with either ambiguity aversion or

insensitivity, it can inform policymakers on how to increase medical take up (for example, by improving people's understanding of uncertainty).

6 Preliminary content of the LISS panel survey questions (optional)

There will be 3 parts.

The first part will be adapted from the the study "Household decisions over the life-cycle" (Hans-Martin von Gaudecker; Christian Zimpelmann; Axel Wogrolly). The exact description is here:

https://www.dataarchive.lissdata.nl/hosted_files/download/7129. The questions have the form:

Do you prefer to win €20 if [EVENT DESCRIPTION] or with [X]% chance?

A. *if [EVENT DESCRIPTION].*

B. *with [X]% chance.*

[EVENT DESCRIPTION] and [X] will vary. As in the previous study, there will be 6 different event descriptions and for each one, 3 to 4 X values. The event descriptions will refer to whether someone, with whom they share many characteristics (their 'virtual twin') will bear various levels of health care expenditures the following year.

[Personalized Information Treatment]

Think about an individual who has, on average, the same characteristics as you. Think about someone who shares with you the same gender, age, background, and other demographic characteristics.

Based on these characteristics, which are the same as ours, on average, this person spends €XX every year as health expenditures.

[Care-seeking behavior]

How often will you use the following health services over the next 12 months?

When you will not use the service, please enter 0.

family physician

psychiatrist/psychologist/psychotherapist

medical specialist at a hospital

physiotherapist

dentist

homecare[Insurance choices]

Will you take out a complementary health insurance in [current year*] (for instance for dentistry, physiotherapy or alternative medicine)?

In [next year*] you have an **obliged** risk of 385 euro. Besides a **voluntary** own risk is possible. How much will be your voluntary own risk in [next year*]?

References

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